

EUROPEAN MIDDLEWARE INITIATIVE

PSEUDONYMITY SERVICE REFERENCE CARD

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EMI Component Version:	1.1.0
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EMI Pseudonymity Service Reference Card

Service Reference Card (Pseudonymity Service 1.1.0 for EMI-2)

- **Functional description:** Hides users' real identity behind a pseudonymous identity
- **Services running:**
 - ◆ Java application `org.glite.pseudo.standalone.PseudonymityService`
- **Init scripts and options:**
 - ◆ `/etc/init.d/pseudonymity-service {start|stop|status|restart}`
- **Configuration files location with example:**
 - ◆ **Config directory:** `/etc/pseudonymity/server`
 - ◇ **Template:** `pseudonymity-server.ini`
 - ◆ **Logging directory:** `/var/log/pseudonymity/server`
 - ◇ **Logging configuration:** `/etc/pseudonymity/server/logging.xml`
- **Open ports:**
 - ◆ **Service port:** `*:8443`
 - ◆ **Admin port:** `localhost:8444`
- **Possible unit test of the service:** None
- **Where is service state held (and can it be rebuilt):** The service state is in memory, no persistency provided.
- **Cron jobs:** None
- **Security information**
 - ◆ Access control mechanism (authentication & authorization):
 - ◇ Authentication: SSL/TLS client authentication on the service port
 - ◇ Authorization: Configured in the configuration file (subject DN and/or VOMS attributes)
 - ◆ How to block/ban a user
 - ◇ Not supported, except via certificate revocation
 - ◆ Network Usage
 - ◇ TCP traffic to the service port, outgoing TCP traffic to the online CA, attribute authority and possibly audit database.
 - ◆ Firewall configuration
 - ◇ The service port should be open for TCP traffic.
 - ◆ Security recommendations
 - ◆ Security incompatibilities
 - ◆ List of externals (packages are NOT maintained by Red Hat)
 - ◆ Other security relevant comments
- **Utility scripts:** None
- **Location of reference documentation for users:**
 - ◆ **Configuration:** `PseudonymityClientConfiguration`
 - ◆ **User Guide:** `PseudonymityClientUserGuide`
- **Location of reference documentation for administrators:**
 - ◆ **Configuration:** `PseudonymityServerConfiguration`
 - ◆ **Operation:** `PseudonymityServerOperation`

This topic: EMI > PseudonymitySRC

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